

**A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF EFFECTIVENESS OF CO-OPERATIVE LEARNING METHOD
AND TRADITIONAL TEACHING METHOD AT HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL
IN JALGAON CITY**

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Abstract: *The present research deals with A Comparative Study of Effectiveness of Co-operative learning Method and Traditional Teaching Method at Higher Secondary School in Jalgaon City The samples Sixty (60) students of XI class in Higher Secondary School. The data was analyzed using t.*

Findings : *Co-operative learning Method is an effective for teaching of in secondary students.*

Keywords: *Co-operative learning Method and Traditional Teaching Method*

Introduction:

Teacher play very prominent role in molding up tomorrow's citizen, the teachers should possess training in using the most modern Method in the field of education. Learning is social, sharing and caring and these are the main aims of learning.

One of the four aspects of the pillars of learning is to live together. Our class room teaching must develop the students to realize the importance of living together. Co-operative learning approach (which comes under social interaction family) is one such approach, in which small teams each with students of different levels of ability, use a variety of learning activities to improve their understanding of a subject.

Each member of a team is responsible not only for learning what is taught but also for helping teammates learn, thus creating an atmosphere of achievement. Co-operative learning has been shown to be effective for developing rich content knowledge, students' higher level thinking strategies and abilities to work independently. It provides situations for students to teach each other. When students explain and teach concepts to each other, retention of these concepts improves Hence the investigators selected the topic A Comparative Study of Effectiveness of Co-operative learning Method and Traditional Teaching Method at Higher Secondary School

Statement of the Problem

A Comparative Study of Effectiveness of Co-operative learning Method and Traditional Teaching Method at Higher Secondary School in Jalgaon City

Objective

1. To compare the mean scores of the control group and ex-per mental group in their post test.

Hypotheses:

There is no significant difference between the post test scores of the control group (Traditional method) and experimental group (Co-operative learning Method).

Methodology of the study: The investigator adopted experimental method for the present study. Sixty (60) students of XI class in Higher Secondary School (Science) were selected for a sample and sample was divided into two group namely experiment and control group. The experimental group consisted 30 students who were taught Co-operative learning Method and the control group comprising 30 students was taught by the conventional method of teaching.

Design Sixty (60) students of XI class in Higher Secondary School (Science) selected for a sample and sample was divided into two group namely experiment and control group. Post test experimental design.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The results obtained in the experiment were tabulated and have been presented in the form of table and discuss below:

Hypotheses 01: There is no significant difference between the post test scores of the control group (Traditional method) and experimental group (Co-operative learning Method).

Group	N	Mean	S.D.	Table 't' value	Obtained 't' value	Accepted/ Rejected
Control	30	09.23	3.41	2.00	6.10	Rejected
Experimental	30	17.56	2.33			

Interpretation

From the results of Table No. 1.1, it can be seen that, Control group (Traditional) and Experimental group (Co-operative learning Method) do not differ significantly with their mean score of post test ($t=6.10$) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. On the basis of obtain 't' value; we can say that, there is significant difference between the post test scores of the control group (Traditional method) and experimental group (Co-operative learning Method).

• Finding:

The result of the present study clearly point out the significant increase in the mean scores has been found in the post test scores of the experimental group. Significance differences have been found between the control and experimental group on post test scores. The experimental group, which was taught by the Co-operative learning Method showed better learning. The conclusion is evident that the Co-operative learning Method is an effective for teaching of in secondary students.

Reference

1. Best, J.W. & Kahn, J.V. (2006). *Research in Education* (9th Ed.). New Delhi: Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd.
2. Kerlinger, F.N. (1979). *Foundations of Behavioral Research* (3rd Ed). New York: Holt, Rinehart & Winston.
3. Kothari, C.R. (1990) *Research Methodology, Methods and Techniques*. New Delhi: Wiley Eastern Limited.
4. Mangal, S. K. (2002). *Advanced Psychology* (1st Ed.). New Delhi: Prentice Hall of India, Private Limited.